

Tidally Excited Oscillations of Heartbeat Stars: Pulsation Phases

Zhao Guo^{1,2,3}

¹ Center for Exoplanets and Habitable Worlds, 525 Davey Laboratory, The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16802, USA

² Copernicus Astronomical Center, Polish Academy of Sciences, Bartycka 18, 00-716 Warsaw, Poland

³ Center for High Angular Resolution Astronomy and Department of Physics and Astronomy, Georgia State University, P.O. Box 5060, Atlanta, GA 30302-5060, USA

Abstract

We examine the pulsation phases of tidally excited oscillations (TEOs) in heartbeat binary stars. The target list includes four published heartbeat binaries and two additional systems observed by *Kepler*. To the first order, the pulsation phases of TEOs can be explained by the geometric effect of the dominant $l = 2$, $m = 0$, or ± 2 modes. We found that this simple theoretical interpretation can account for most of the systems in the list, assuming their spin and orbit axis are aligned. We do find strong deviations from the predictions for the misaligned system KIC8624262.

1 Introduction

More than half of all stars reside in binaries and tides can have a significant effect on stellar oscillations. In the first version of the classical textbook *Nonradial oscillations of stars*, there is a whole chapter on tidal oscillations (Unno et al. 1979). However, it was removed in the second version (Unno et al. 1989), probably owing to the notion that such oscillations are hard to be observed.

Tides can induce the internal gravity waves (Zahn 1977; Goldreich & Nicholson 1989; Goodman & Dickson 1998; Ogilvie 2014) in early-type stars. These waves dissipate in the radiative envelope and the surface, and this is manifested as the synchronization and circularization of binaries. The direct manifestation of tides can be shown in the light curves as flux variations. The theoretical foundations have been laid out several decades ago (e.g., Press & Teukolsky 1977), Kumar et al. (1995) even derived the expression for the observed flux variations from the tidal response. However, it is only after the *Kepler* satellite that we are able to observe the tidally excited oscillations (TEOs) unambiguously. The prototype system KOI-54 (Welsh et al. 2011), inspired lots of interests in observations (Hambleton et al. 2013, 2016, 2017) and subsequent theoretical studies (Fuller & Lai 2012; Burkart et al. 2012; O’Leary & Burkart 2012; Fuller 2017; Penoyre & Stone 2018). Thompson et al. (2011) presented tens of such so called ‘heartbeat’ stars and the Kepler Eclipsing Binary (EB) Catalog (Slawson et al. 2011; Prša et al. (2011); Kirk et al. 2016) now consists of 173 such systems, flagged as ‘HBs’. Out of them, about 24 systems show tidally excited oscillations (TEOs)¹, flagged as ‘TPs’.

Pulsation phases contain important information on the mode properties. When observed in multi-colour photometry, the phase difference in difference passbands, along with the amplitude ratios, can be used to identify the pulsation modes. In binary stars, phase modulation can be used to detect the companions and derive orbital parameters. This has been applied to hundreds of binary stars as well as star-planet systems (Murphy et al. 2016, 2018). Bowman et al. (2016) and Zong et al. (2016) demonstrate that the amplitude and phase variations can be used to infer properties on the mode coupling, leading to the realm of non-linear asteroseismology. The ratio between the flux variation and the radial displacement on the stellar surface, i.e., the non-adiabatic pa-

rameter f , is a complex parameter, and its phase information is used in the so-called ‘complex asteroseismic modeling’ (Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz et al. 2003; Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz & Walczak 2010). The phase changes due to eclipses in binary stars have the potential to facilitate the mode identification in the eclipsing systems (eclipse mapping, Biro & Nusp 2011).

The HBs with TEOs are ideal laboratories to study the effect of equilibrium and dynamical tides. Only a few systems have been studied in detail, and the phase information is usually neglected. In this paper, we examine the pulsation phases of TEOs in six HB systems and try to extract information on the mode identification.

2 Analysis

2.1 Equations

Burkart et al. (2012) and O’Leary & Burkart (2014) have derived the expressions for the pulsation amplitudes and phases of TEOs for adiabatic modes (see also Guo et al. 2017), and Fuller (2017) extended it to the non-adiabatic modes and spin-orbit misaligned cases.

Under the assumptions that:

- 1) The pulsations are adiabatic;
- 2) The pulsation, spin, and orbit axis are all aligned;
- 3) The observed TEOs are standing waves,

the pulsation phases of TEOs for the dominant $l = 2$ modes can be expressed as:

$$\phi_{l=2,m} = \begin{cases} 0.25 + m\phi_0 & \text{if } m = 2 \text{ or } -2 \\ 0.25 & \text{if } m = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\phi_0 = 0.25 - \omega_p/(2\pi)$.

All phases are measured with respect to the time of periastron passage T_{peri} and are in units of 2π . We cannot distinguish between $m = 2$ and $m = -2$ modes only from the phases as there is a 180° phase ambiguity (Burkart et al. 2012). In the following, we use $m = 2$ and $m = -2$ equivalently, unless we specify the mode is prograde or retrograde.

By examining the eq. (1), we can see that accurate T_{peri} and ω_p are needed to identify the pulsation modes from their phases. These two parameters can be obtained from radial velocity (RV) measurements as well as from the light curves

¹Or called Tidally Induced Pulsations

Figure 1: Amplitude ratio of $l = 2, m = 0$ and $l = 2, m = 2$ modes as a function of orbital inclination. The dotted line indicates an amplitude ratio of 1.0.

(LCs).

The dominant TEOs have a spherical degree $l = 2$, but which azimuthal number, m , do we expect? If the spin/pulsation and orbital axis is aligned, then only $m = 0$ and $m = \pm 2$ modes are excited. And if we only consider the geometric effect, the observed mode amplitude is proportional to $\sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)(l-m)!}{4\pi(l+m)!}} P_l^m(\cos i)$. When evaluated at $l = 2$ and $m = 0, 2$, the amplitude ratio can be expressed as:

$$A_{m=0}/A_{m=2} = \frac{0.5(3 \cos^2 i - 1)}{\sqrt{24}(1 - \cos^2 i)} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 shows the running of the amplitude ratio as a function of orbital inclination i . At low inclinations ($i < \approx 30$), $m = 0$ modes are strongly favoured. But at the intermediate to high inclination, both $m = 0$ and $m = 2$ are expected, except for a limited range $i \approx 51^\circ - 58^\circ$ when the $m = 0$ modes reach the lowest amplitude contrast ($A_{m=0}/A_{m=2} < 5$).

2.2 Method

We de-trended the Kepler light curves (LCs) following the treatment in Guo et al. (2016, 2017). The de-trended LCs were fitted with the Kumar light curve model (Kumar et al. 1995) to derive the estimated T_{peri} , e , ω_p , and the orbital inclination i . These parameters can also be derived from the radial velocities (RVs) except for i . The orbital period is adopted as the values in the Kepler EB catalog. We use the literature values for the above parameters if available. We specify the source as LC or (LC+RV) in Table 1-6. Note that we only need T_{peri} and ω_p for the calculation of theoretical phases. The error bars on T_{peri} and ω_p are propagated to the theoretical values of TEO phases ϕ_m . The binary light curve model was subtracted from the de-trended light curves, and the Fourier spectrum of the residuals was calculated with the *Period04* package (Lenz & Berger 2005). A standard pre-whitening procedure was performed to derive the pulsation frequency, amplitudes, and phases. We fit the background noise in the Fourier spectrum in the log-log space, using a Lorentzian-like equation in Pablo et al. (2017). The uncertainties on the frequencies, amplitudes, and phases are estimated following Kallinger et al. (2008). The theoretical pulsation phases ϕ_m for $m = 0, 2$ and -2 are calculated, plotted in Figure 3, 5, 6-9 as vertical strips, and listed in Table 1-6.

Figure 2: Phase-folded Kepler light curve of KIC8719324 and its Fourier spectrum. The two dominant TEOs at 26 and 29 times of orbital frequency are labeled.

Figure 3: Pulsation Phases of the two TEOs in KIC8719324. The phases of the 26 and 29 orbital harmonics agree with the theoretical predictions for $l = 2, m = 0$ and $m = 2$ modes, respectively.

3 Results

3.1 KIC8719324

KIC8719324 is a short period binary with $P \approx 10$ days. Figure 1 shows the phase-folded *Kepler* light curve. The dip and bump have a similar amplitude which signatures a system with an intermediate-to-high inclination angle. A fit with the Kumar light curve model yields an inclination of 73° . The orbital parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Strong oscillations are present, even in the phased folded light curve, indicating frequencies are of integer times of orbital frequency. The Fourier spectrum in the bottom panel of Fig. 1 shows two dominating TEOs at $N = 26$ and $N = 29$ orbital harmonics. The pulsation phases of these two TEOs shown in Fig.2 suggest that they are $m = 0$ and $m = 2$ modes, respectively. This is in line with an intermediate-to-high inclination, for which both $m = 0$ and $m = 2$ modes are expected, but $|m| = 2$ modes are preferred (larger amplitude). The two frequencies at $f < 1 \text{ day}^{-1}$ are likely due to rotational modulations.

3.2 KIC9016693

Figure 3 shows the light curve of KIC 9016693. It is a 26-day binary system, with an eccentricity of about 0.7. The overall shape of the LC is a near-symmetric periastron brightening, indicating that it is nearly a face-on system. We

Figure 4: Phase-folded Kepler light curve of KIC 9016693 and its Fourier spectrum. The dominant TEO at 24 times of orbital frequency is labeled.

Figure 5: Pulsation Phases of the dominant TEOs in KIC9016693. The phase of the 24 orbital harmonics agrees with the theoretical predictions for a $l = 2, m = 0$ mode.

obtain an inclination of 25 degrees from the Kumar model fit to the LC.

A very strong pulsation in the LC reaches an amplitude of 0.2 milli-mag, and this strong sinusoidal shape of pulsation distorts the underlying binary light curve (the brightening feature). This dominating pulsation has a frequency of $f = 0.91 \text{ day}^{-1}$, which is exact 24 times of orbital frequency $f_{orb} = 0.03792 \text{ day}^{-1}$. The pulsation phase is 0.275, which is very close to the prediction for an $m = 0$ mode ($\phi = 0.25$), and this complies with the low inclination angle of the binary.

3.3 Four Published Heartbeat Stars with TEOs

The face-on system, KOI-54, have been discussed thoroughly in Fuller & Lai (2012), Burkart et al. (2012) and Oleary & Burkart (2014). The two dominant TEOs have been identified as $l = 2, m = 0$ modes. The edge-on system KIC3230227, presented in Guo et al. (2017), shows more than ten TEOs. Most of them are orbital harmonics and can be explained by $l = 2, m = 2$ prograde modes.

Except for the above two systems, a few other heartbeat binary stars have been characterized in detail. But no discussions on the pulsation phases are presented. Pablo et al. (2017) modeled the pulsation amplitudes of the TEOs in ι Ori and found they agree with $l = 2, m = 2$ modes. In this section, we present the pulsation phase analysis of TEOs in four published heartbeat binary systems.

HD 209295: (Figure 6, Table 3)

This 3-day, eccentric ($e = 35$) binary was studied in great detail in Handler et al. (2002). Although there is no ‘heartbeat’ light curve for this system, this binary was observed in multiple colours (B, V, and I-band). The Fourier spectrum shows five significant TEOs ranging from 3 to 9 times of orbital frequency.

We show the pulsation phases in three passbands in Figure 5. Although the $N = 3, 5, 9$ orbital harmonic TEOs agree with $|m|=2$, the one with the largest amplitude ($N = 9$) is probably an $m = 0$ mode. Handler et al. (2002) only constrained the inclination as $i < (40^\circ - 45^\circ)$, and at this intermediate inclination, both $m = 0$ and $m = 2$ modes can reach observable amplitudes. The theoretical modeling of the tidally excited radial velocity amplitude (Willems & Aerts 2002) presented in Section 5.2 indicates that TEOs at $N = 3$ times of orbital frequency may be account for by an $l = 2, m = -2$ mode. This is in agreement with our phase measurement here. The observed pulsation phases do not seem to depend on the passbands, in line with the theoretical interpretation that it is only a geometric effect.

KIC 3749404: (Figure 7, Table 4)

This 20-day, eccentric ($e = 0.635$), and fastly precessing ($\dot{\omega} = 1.2^\circ \text{ yr}^{-1}$) binary has an intermediate inclination $i = 62^\circ$ (Hambleton et al. 2016). This orientation slightly favours the $m = 2$ modes but $m = 0$ modes cannot be excluded. Our phase measurements suggest that: the $N = 19, 20, 21, 22, 26, 27$ TEOs have phases close to $|m| = 2$ modes, and the $N = 17, 23$ TEOs are probably $m = 0$ modes.

ι Ori: (Figure 8, Table 5)

We use the results presented in Pablo et al. (2017). The orbital and physical parameters of the binary are listed in their Table 2, and the frequencies, amplitudes, and phases of TEOs are listed in Table 3. We did not include the frequency at $f = 6f_{orb}$, since this peak is likely from the instrumental effect or data reduction and not likely a real TEO frequency.

We show the pulsation phases of TEOs at $N = 23, 25, 27, 33$ orbital harmonics in Figure 8. The phase measurements from the telescope pointing (Orion I) have large error bars, excluding us from making reliable mode identification. Both the red and blue filter measurements indicate $N = 25$ is probably an $m = -2$ mode. For $N = 23$ and $N = 33$ TEOs, the phases at both telescope pointings (Orion I and II) are not consistent.

The pulsation amplitude modeling of TEOs presented Pablo et al. (2017) suggests these four TEOs are likely $m = 2$ prograde modes. The phase information mentioned above is not in contradiction with this argument. Better measurements of pulsation phases are needed to make future interpretations.

KIC 8164262: (Figure 9, Table 6)

The argument of periastron of this binary ($\omega_p = 85^\circ$) happens to be close to 90° , so that the theoretical phases of $|m| = 2$ mode are close to the $m = 0$ modes at $\phi = 0.25, 0.75$. However, the measured pulsation phases do not have the tendency to cluster around the two expected phases (Figure 9). This can be explained by the following: Firstly, assuming the rotational modulation signature in the light curve arises from the primary star, Hambleton et al. (2017) derived the inclination of the primary star to be $i = 35^\circ$. But the orbital inclination of the binary is 65° , so a strong spin-orbit misalignment is present in the system. Since the pulsation is from the primary star, and the pulsation axis is usually aligned with the spin axis, the observed pulsations of TEOs cannot be modeled with the simplified equation in Section 2. Secondly, Fuller et al. (2017) showed that the TEOs in KIC 8164262 are likely in

Figure 6: Pulsation Phases of the dominant TEOs in HD209295 in B (blue), V (yellow), and I-band (red).

Figure 7: Pulsation Phases of the TEOs in KIC3749404.

strong resonance locking, i.e., the evolution of pulsation frequencies is in concert with the evolution of the binary orbit and the stellar spin, so that the modes are always in resonance with the driving frequency from the companion. If the modes are in strong resonance locking, their phases can be arbitrary. A detailed modeling of the pulsation phases for the misaligned cases is detailed in Fuller (2017) and is subject to a future study.

4 Discussions

The pulsation phase analysis of HBs with TEOs in this paper is by no means complete. Other HBs with TEOs include KIC4544587 (Hambleton et al. 2013), Maceroni et al (2009), etc. There is also some evidence of TEOs in η Carina (Richardson et al. 2018). TEOs have also been discovered in exoplanet-host stars, such as WASP 33 in Collier Cameron et al. (2010) and HAT-P-2 in de Wit et al. (2017). We plan to present a complete pulsation phase analysis of TEOs in Kepler HBs in a future paper, including the non-adiabatic and misalignment effect in the phase calculations.

In order to model the TEOs in detail, fundamental parameters such as the mass, radius, effective temperature, and orbital parameters are required. There are already spectroscopic observations of HBs (Smullen & Kobulnicky 2015; Dimitrov et al. 2017). An updated radial velocity follow-up on Shporer et al. (2016) is underway (Guo et al. in prep.). The full LC+RV analysis can yield the parameters needed above, but the binary modeling is non-trivial and has to be done on a one-by-one basis.

There are also non-orbital-harmonic TEOs present in the

Figure 8: Pulsation Phases of the TEOs in ι Ori. The upper and lower panel show the measurements in the two telescope pointings Orion II and Orion I, respectively. Blue and red symbols indicate the measured phases in the blue and red filter of the BRITE satellite.

Figure 9: Pulsation Phases of the TEOs in KIC 8164262. The phase of the TEOs do not comply with the theoretical predictions for aligned systems.

HBs as shown in KOI-54 and KIC 3230227. The variations of amplitudes and phases can offer us information on the mode damping and mode coupling. Detailed seismic modeling also requires the accurate physical parameter to be measured first. By utilizing the amplitude equations, an analysis on the non-linear mode coupling like the one in Oleary & Burkart (2014) and Weinberg et al. (2013) can be performed and is highly desirable.

Table 1: KIC8719324

Parameter	KIC8719324	-	-	-
Period (days)	10.2326979			
T_0 (EB catalog)	55003.805236			
	(LC, Kumar)			
T_{peri} (BJD-2,400,000)	55004.0099(2)			
e , Orbital eccentricity	0.5998(1)			
ω_p , argument of periastron ($^\circ$)	-17.123(32)			
i , Orbital inclination ($^\circ$)	73.54(6)			
T_{eff} (K)	7750			
$\log g$ (cgs)	4.5			
TEOs	$N (= f/f_{orb})$	Frequency, f (day^{-1})	Amplitude (10^{-3})	Phase (2π)
	26	2.540879(5)	0.64472(8)	0.26(1)
	29	2.83407(4)	0.0789(6)	0.87(4)
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.34, 0.84			
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.16, 0.66			
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25, 0.75			

Table 2: KIC9016693

Parameter	KIC9016693	-	-	-
Period (days)	26.3680271			
T_0 (EB catalog)	55002.583038			
	(LC, Kumar)	(RVs, Shporer et al. 2016)		
T_{peri}	55002.436(16)	57268.91(10)		
e , Orbital eccentricity	0.725(6)	0.596(18)		
ω_p , argument of periastron (degree)	102.8(17)	108.4(17)		
i , Orbital inclination (degree)	25.6(8)	-		
T_{eff} (K)	7262_{327}^{+201}			
$\log g$ (cgs)	-			
TEOs	$N (= f/f_{orb})$	Frequency (day^{-1})	Amplitude (10^{-3})	Phase (2π)
	24	0.910593(7)	0.19238(6)	0.275(10)
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.148, 0.648			
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.352, 0.852			
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25, 0.75			

Table 3: HD 209295

Parameter	HD 209295	Handler et al. (2002)	-	-
P (days)	3.10575(10)			
T_0	-			
	(LC)	(RVs)		
T_{peri}	-	51771.864(14)		
e , Orbital eccentricity	-	0.352(11)		
ω_p , argument of periastron (degree)	-	31.1(20)		
i , Orbital inclination (degree)	-	< 40-45		
T_{eff} (K)	7750			
$\log g$ (cgs)	4.3			
TEOs	$N (= f/f_{orb})$	Frequency (d^{-1})	Amplitude (10^{-3}mag)	Phase (2π)
	8	2.57593(11)	18.3(3)	0.185(2)
	7	2.25394(11)	8.4(3)	0.006(5)
	3	0.96597(11)	7.0(3)	0.891(6)
	5	1.60996(11)	4.6(3)	0.550(9)
	9	2.89792(11)	4.5(3)	0.131(9)
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.077, 0.577			
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.423, 0.923			
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25, 0.75			

Table 4: KIC3749404

Parameter	KIC3749404	-	-	-
P (days)	20.3063852			
T_0 (EB catalog)	54981.16619			
	(LC, Kumar)	(RVs+LC, Hambleton et al. 2016)		
T_{peri}	54981.5723(2)	-		
e , Orbital eccentricity	0.635(5)	0.659(6)		
ω_p , argument of periastron (degree)	121.6(3)	123.2(23)		
i , Orbital inclination (degree)	37.31(7)	62(1)		
T_{eff} (K)	8000(300)			
	6900(300)			
$\log g$ (cgs)	4.10(3)			
	4.40(4)			
TEOs	N ($= f/f_{\text{orb}}$)	Frequency (d^{-1})	Amplitude (10^{-5})	Phase (2π)
	21	1.034138(3)	8.068(4)	0.88(1)
	20	0.984898(4)	6.699(9)	0.93(1)
	26	1.280378(6)	3.739(27)	0.067(19)
	22	1.083385(5)	4.908(29)	0.87(2)
	19	0.93563(1)	2.66(7)	0.92(3)
	7	0.34475(3)	2.1(2)	0.05(9)
	24	1.181864(7)	3.47(6)	0.65(2)
	23	1.132624(7)	3.44(7)	0.71(2)
	5	0.24624(6)	1.21(62)	0.22(19)
	17	0.83716 (3)	0.96(36)	0.79(10)
	27	1.32963(2)	0.91(28)	0.92(8)
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.066	0.566		
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.434,	0.934		
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25,	0.75		

Table 5: ι Orionis

Parameter	ι Orionis	Pablo et al. (2017)
P (days)	29.13376	
T_{peri} (HJD-2400000)	51121.658(fixed)	
e , Orbital eccentricity	$0.7452^{+0.0010}_{-0.0014}$	
ω_p , argument of periastron (degree)	122.15(11)	
i , Orbital inclination (degree)	$62.86^{+0.17}_{-0.14}$	
T_{eff} (K)	31000	
	18319^{+531}_{-758}	
TEOs	N ($= f/f_{\text{orb}}$)	Table 3 in Pablo et al. (2017)
	23	
	25	
	27	
	33	
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.071,	0.571
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.429,	0.929
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25,	0.75

Table 6: KIC8164262

Parameter	KIC8164262	-	-	-
P (days)	87.4571700(6381)			
T_0 (EB catalog)	54969.411534			
	(LC)	(LC+RVs, Hambleton et al. 2017)		
T_{peri}		55668.829		
e , Orbital eccentricity	-	0.886(3)		
ω_p , argument of periastron ($^\circ$)	-	84.79(57)		
i , Orbital inclination ($^\circ$)	-	65(1)		
T_{eff} (K)	6890(80), 3500			
$\log g$ (cgs)	3.9(1)			
TEOs	N ($= f/f_{orb}$)	Frequency (d^{-1})	Amplitude (10^{-5})	Phase (2π)
	229	2.6184922(3)	1010(20)	0.4526(2)
	241	2.755 699(9)	35.3(8)	0.723(3)
	123	1.406 45(1)	22.9(9)	0.601(5)
	158	1.806 65(2)	15.2(8)	0.331(8)
	124	1.417 86(2)	15.1(9)	0.852(10)
	132	1.509 33(2)	13.3(9)	0.840(10)
	194	2.218 31(2)	12.3(8)	0.196(11)
	128	1.463 60(3)	11.8(9)	0.419(11)
	317	3.624 72(3)	9.5(8)	0.384(13)
	129	1.475 01(4)	8.3(9)	0.889(16)
	125	1.429 31(4)	6.9(9)	0.920(16)
	137	1.566 44(4)	6.8(8)	0.366(16)
	114	1.303 55(5)	6.4(8)	0.761(16)
	264	3.018 70(6)	5.6(8)	0.507(16)
	22	0.251 21(5)	5.6(8)	0.729(16)
$\phi_{m=2}$ (2π)	0.279, 0.779			
$\phi_{m=-2}$ (2π)	0.221, 0.221			
$\phi_{m=0}$ (2π)	0.25, 0.75			

Acknowledgments

We thank Jim Fuller, Gerald Hander, and Eric Ford for helpful discussions.

References

- Bíró, I. B., & Nuspl, J. 2011, *MNRAS*, 416, 1601
- Bowman, D. M., Kurtz, D. W., Breger, M., Murphy, S. J., & Holdsworth, D. L. 2016, *MNRAS*, 460, 1970
- Burkart, J., Quataert, E., Arras, P., & Weinberg, N. N. 2012, *MNRAS*, 421, 983
- Collier Cameron, A., Guenther, E., Smalley, B., et al. 2010, *MNRAS*, 407, 507
- Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz, J., Dziembowski, W. A., & Pamyatnykh, A. A. 2003, *A&A*, 407, 999
- Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz, J., & Walczak, P. 2010, *MNRAS*, 403, 496
- de Wit, J., Lewis, N. K., Knutson, H. A., et al. 2017, *ApJ*, 836, L17
- Dimitrov, D. P., Kjurkchieva, D. P., & Iliev, I. K. 2017, *MNRAS*, 469, 2089
- Fuller, J., & Lai, D. 2012, *MNRAS*, 420, 3126
- Fuller, J. 2017, *MNRAS*, 472, 1538
- Fuller, J., Hambleton, K., Shporer, A., Isaacson, H., & Thompson, S. 2017, *MNRAS*, 472, L25
- Goldreich, P., & Nicholson, P. D. 1989, *ApJ*, 342, 1079
- Goodman, J., & Dickson, E. S. 1998, *ApJ*, 507, 938
- Guo, Z., Gies, D. R., Matson, R. A., & García Hernández, A. 2016, *ApJ*, 826, 69
- Guo, Z., Gies, D. R., & Fuller, J. 2017, *ApJ*, 834, 59
- Hambleton, K. M., Kurtz, D. W., Prša, A., et al. 2013, *MNRAS*, 434, 925
- Hambleton, K., Kurtz, D. W., Prša, A., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 463, 1199
- Hambleton, K., Fuller, J., Thompson, S., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 473, 5165
- Handler, G., Balona, L. A., Shobbrook, R. R., et al. 2002, *MNRAS*, 333, 262
- Kallinger, T., Reegen, P., & Weiss, W. W. 2008, *A&A*, 481, 571
- Kirk, B., Conroy, K., Prša, A., et al. 2016, *AJ*, 151, 68
- Kumar, P., Ao, C. O., & Quataert, E. J. 1995, *ApJ*, 449, 294
- Lenz, P., & Breger, M. 2005, *Communications in Asteroseismology*, 146, 53
- Maceroni, C., Montalbán, J., Michel, E., et al. 2009, *A&A*, 508, 1375
- Murphy, S. J., Bedding, T. R., & Shibahashi, H. 2016, *ApJ*, 827, L17
- Murphy, S. J., Moe, M., Kurtz, D. W., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 474, 4322
- Ogilvie, G. I. 2014, *ARA&A*, 52, 171
- O’Leary, R. M., & Burkart, J. 2014, *MNRAS*, 440, 3036
- Pablo, H., Richardson, N. D., Fuller, J., et al. 2017, *MNRAS*, 467, 2494
- Penoyre, Z., & Stone, N. C. 2018, arXiv:1803.05917
- Press, W. H., & Teukolsky, S. A. 1977, *ApJ*, 213, 183
- Prša, A., Batalha, N., Slawson, R. W., et al. 2011, *AJ*, 141, 83
- Richardson, N. D., Pablo, H., Sterken, C., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 475, 5417
- Shporer, A., Fuller, J., Isaacson, H., et al. 2016, *ApJ*, 829, 34
- Slawson, R. W., Prša, A., Welsh, W. F., et al. 2011, *AJ*, 142, 160
- Smullen, R. A., & Kobulnicky, H. A. 2015, *ApJ*, 808, 166
- Thompson, S. E., Everett, M., Mullally, F., et al. 2012, *ApJ*, 753, 86
- Unno, W., Osaki, Y., Ando, H., & Shibahashi, H. 1979, Tokyo, University of Tokyo Press; Forest Grove, Ore., ISBS, Inc., 1979. 330 p.,
- Unno, W., Osaki, Y., Ando, H., Saio, H., & Shibahashi, H. 1989, *Nonradial oscillations of stars*, Tokyo: University of Tokyo Press, 1989, 2nd ed.,
- Weinberg, N. N., Arras, P., & Burkart, J. 2013, *ApJ*, 769, 121
- Welsh, W. F., Orosz, J. A., Aerts, C., et al. 2011, *ApJS*, 197, 4
- Zahn, J.-P. 1977, *A&A*, 57, 383
- Zong, W., Charpinet, S., & Vauclair, G. 2016, *A&A*, 594, A46